

HOFIZI ABRU AND THE HISTORY OF THE TIMURIDS PERIOD IN HIS WORKS

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Annotation: The article provides insights into Hofizi Abru and his works, shedding light on the historical and scholarly sources of the Timurid era. Through the works of Hofizi Abru, valuable information about the life of Amir Timur and the Timurids is presented, drawing on historical and scientific references.

Key words: Amir Timur, Timurids, Middle Ages, sources, Hofizi Abru, Zafarnama, Mawarannahr, Khurasan, historian, historical heritage.

Introduction: The study of the history of Amir Timur and the Timurid era has gained prominence due to independence. This period not only holds significance in terms of political power but has also been elucidated by eminent historians not only within the boundaries of the empire but throughout the entire Eastern world. Among these notable historians are Ghiyath al-Din Ali, Nizam al-Din Shami, Hofizi Abru, Mu'in al-Din Natanz, Sharaf al-Din Ali Yazdi, Abd al-Razzaq Samarqandi, Mirkhond, and Khwandamir. Among these scholars, the position of the historian Hofizi Abru is particularly esteemed.

According to sources, Hofizi Abru began his career as a scribe during one of Amir Timur's campaigns and gradually gained recognition as a knowledgeable scholar and a formidable chess player. He served as the court historian for the Timurids, contributing significantly until the end of his life [1]. Born with the name Shahobuddin Abdullah ibn Lutfilloh ibn Abdurashid al-Khawfi around

1361-1362 in the city of Herat, Afghanistan, according to the information provided by the historian Abdurrazzaq Samarqandi, Hofizi Abru was born and educated in Herat, and he passed away in Zanjon (northwest of Iran) in 1430 (1431) [2].

Throughout his life, Hofizi Abru embarked on numerous journeys, exploring regions from Europe to India, traversing the Caucasus, and visiting various provinces of contemporary Russia. He documented his extensive travels, noting, "On horseback, I traveled from north-western Mawarannahr to Turkistan, the Qipchaq Steppe, Khurasan, Iraq, Azerbaijan, Iran, Mug'on, Gurjistan, Greater and Lesser Armenia, the entire territories of Russia and Syria, the shores of the Caspian Sea, the hills of the Caspian, the shores of the Black Sea, and to the east, the Zobul and Kobul regions... I witnessed Delhi, the greatest city of India, several times, and traveled as far as the banks of the Ganges River" [3].

As the author of the historical work "Zafarnama," Hofizi Abru initially served as a historian at the court of Sohirqiron and later under the reign of Shahrukh Mirza. He engaged in religious discussions with scholars from Herat and Aleppo and gifted precious items to those who did not share his beliefs. Notably, Amir Timur engaged in a heated debate with Sharafiddin Halabi, whom he later protected and rewarded with valuable gifts. The number of gifts given by Amir Timur reached nearly 2000 [4]. Therefore, it can be concluded that Hofizi Abru gained the trust of Sohirqiron, becoming a close associate and a reliable companion in the court. He played a significant role as a supporter during Amir Timur's campaigns, and he enjoyed a good rapport with the scholar-king Shahrukh Mirza.

The historian Hofizi Abru is recognized as the author of several historical and historical-geographical works, including "Zayli Zafarnomai Shomiy," "Zayli

Jome' ut-tavorix," "Tarixi Hofizi Abru," "Majmua at-tavorixi sultoniya," and "Zubdat ut-tavorixi Boysung'uriy."

Hofizi Abru wrote two works commissioned by Shahrukh Mirza. One of them is a historical-geographical compilation created between 1414-1420. This work, initially written in Arabic during the 10th century, is known as "Kitob al-masolik va-l-mamolik," attributed to Hasan ibn Ahmad Muhallabi. In 1414, Shahrukh Mirza commissioned Hofizi Abru to translate and revise this work, infusing it with new information [5]. The value of this work lies not only in its translation but also in the addition of fresh insights. Besides being a translation, it incorporates new information, presenting concise political histories alongside descriptions of the geographical conditions of each province.

Hofizi Abru's works provide important details about the geographical situation of each region, including cities such as Bukhara, Samarkand, Nisa, Kashan, Termez, and Khujand. The most significant manuscripts of this work are preserved in libraries in England and Russia (St. Petersburg).

Furthermore, Hofizi Abru is considered one of the historians who continued the narrative series of events from Nizamiddin Shami in his work "Zubdat ut-tavorix." This historical account is regarded as one of the valuable sources on the history of Amir Timur and the Timurid era. Shohruh Mirzo, following the guidance of Hofizi Abru, added additional notes to the works of previous historians like Tabari, Rashiduddin, and Nizamiddin Shami [5].

The work "Zayli Zafarnoma Shomiy" is an appendix to Nizamiddin Shami's "Zafarnoma," covering historical events until February 18, 1405 [6]. "Zayli Jome' ut-tavorix," written in 1417, is a continuation of Rashiduddin Fazlullah's "Jome ut-tavorix," covering the history of Iran from 1304-1370. The famous historical-geographical work "Tarixi Hofizi Abru" includes a world map and other maps, while its gradus (degree) map is particularly significant, recognized by geographers as the masterpiece of Hofizi Abru. This work covers various aspects

of geography and history, providing detailed information about the geography of Khurasan, the detailed geography and history of Fors, Kermon, and Khurasan, as well as the geography of Mawarannahr. It describes cities like Bukhara, Samarkand, Nakhshab, Kashan, Termez, and provides information about rivers like Syr Darya, Amu Darya, and others, along with their widths, lengths, distances, and areas, using different units of measurement such as farsang, monthly road, and daily road [5].

he historian Hofizi Abru wrote a historical work titled "Majmua" ("Compilation"), which was completed between 1423-1427. In this work, he utilized Nizomiddin Shomiy's "Zafarnoma" and continued narrating events up to the year 1420 under the rule of Shohruh Mirzo. Some parts of "Majmua" were published with both the original text and translations by Xonbobo Bayoniy in 1938, F. Tauer in 1959, and K. M. Maytra in 1934.

In 1423, under the decree of Shohruh Mirzo's son Boysungur Mirzo, Hofizi Abru began writing the four-volume work "Majma at-tavorixi sultoniya" ("Collection of Histories Dedicated to the Sultan") and completed it with the events of the year 1427. The four parts of this work include: 1) Prophets and Iranian princes before Islam; 2) Prophet Muhammad and Arab caliphs (up to al-Muhtasim); 3) The history of Iran during the Seljuk and Mongol periods (up to the Elhan Abu Said era); 4) "Zubdat ut-tavorixi Boysunguriy." The fourth part of the work, named "Zubdat ut-tavorixi Boysunguriy" ("The Essence of Boysunguriy's Histories"), specifically highlights the importance of Amir Temur's history and provides details of events up to the year 1427 in Khurasan and Mawarannahr [9].

As of today, three copies of the "Majma at-tavorix" ("Collection of Histories") are known, with one held in the Oxford library, the second in the St. Petersburg Saltikov-Shchedrin library, and the third in the Abu Rayhon Beruni Institute of Oriental Studies of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan. When

these copies are combined, they can reveal the comprehensive content of Hofizi Abru's geography.

The historian Hofizi Abru authored another historical-geographical work between 1414-1420, known as "Hofizi Abru geografiyasi" ("Geography of Hofizi Abru"). In this book, he provided information about the economic activities during the reigns of Amir Temur and Shohruh Mirzo. Currently, some of the scholar's closest works are preserved, and one of them, titled "Geografiya," is held in the Abu Rayhon Beruni Institute of Oriental Studies of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan (Hofizi Abru. Geografiya. O'zR FA ShI, No. 5361). During the era of Uzbekistan's independence, certain excerpts from the work were translated into the Uzbek language [10].

Hofizi Abru's extensive scientific legacy is currently being studied by contemporary scholars. The orientalist O. Boriev, for instance, compiled and translated selected excerpts from Hofizi Abru's works related to the Timurid period in various collections. Additionally, O. Boriev produced a translation of "Zubdat at-tavorix" titled "Amir Temur va Ulug'bek zamondoshlari xotirasida," as well as translated sections from "Zayli Zafarnomai Shomiy," "Geografiya," and Nizomiddin Shomiy's "Zafarnoma." All these translations provide valuable insights into the historical and geographical aspects of the Timurid period [10:B.49].

O. Boriev also completed a doctoral dissertation on Hofizi Abru's geography in 1988. Furthermore, Hofizi Abru's historical legacy has drawn attention not only from Uzbek scholars but also from international researchers. For example, Tajik researcher Rezagolizadex Axangar Narges Vaxab completed a doctoral dissertation in 2005 on the peculiarities of Hofizi Abru's historical views, contributing significantly to the understanding of the scholar and his works [11].

In conclusion, the full exploration of the comprehensive historical and geographical works of Hofizi Abru, which serve as important sources for

understanding the history of the Timurid period, is yet to be fully realized. It is expected that future research will bring forth new and comprehensive scientific investigations in this field.

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